

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SALISU****FIRST NAME: ABDULATEEF****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: (e.g., Microsoft Office Professional Plus 2019 on Windows 10)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

- Concerning referencing using the Zotero software
 - The stand-alone program is adequate for easy saving of references to your library
 - You can add references by adding the listing manually or using an identifier to add the references, or through the connector plugin on a web browser¹**
 - You can stay adequately organized with references without using any other features such as notes tab, tags, collections features
 - The paid version and its plugin offer the complete features for academic writing
- The following are all Grammarly Premium advanced features that can be turned on or off to enhance writing, except

¹ Top Tip Bio, "How to Use Zotero (A Complete Beginner's Guide)" (TopTipBio.com, 2021), 2:48 – 4:54, accessed September 8, 2022, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=v4zujRE98c8>.

- spelling²**
 - plagiarism check
 - overused words
 - repetitive words
3. One of these is not a required step in the process undertaken before starting an academic essay.
- Startup as early as possible and not procrastinate to have enough time to read, research the topic, think, and write
 - Defining the question, analyzing the task, writing everything one knows about a topic
 - Preparing a suitable abstract to capture your final thoughts³**
 - Drafting an initial plan for going about the essay of your initial thoughts and ideas about the research topic for a preliminary essay plan to guide your research
4. One of the steps in essay writing is to prepare a first draft essay structure and framework. Which of the following is not a part of the essay structure
- The "Introduction" introduces the topic areas with general, broad opening sentences and answers the question with a thesis statement while providing a summary or 'road map' of the essay

² Stacey Roshan, "Grammarly Tutorial: Making Use of Grammarly Premium & An Overview of Grammarly for Google Docs" (YouTube video, 2018), accessed September 8, 2022, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FKRBvTOLo1M&t=54s>.

³ Ibid., 7–8.

- The "Body" answers the question by developing a discussion, showing your knowledge and grasp of the material you have read, offering exposition and evidence to develop your argument, and using relevant examples and authoritative quotes
 - The "Conclusion" restates the answer to the question, re-summarizes the main points, and includes a final, broad statement about possible implications, future directions for research
 - The "Conclusion" introduces new information or ideas to round off the essay by summing up⁴**
5. Which of the following most accurately captures the value researchers are looking for when using primary sources of data in their research to test their hypothesis?
- To acquire an overview of a subject matter (tertiary sources)
 - To gather evidence (primary sources)⁵**
 - To learn from other researchers (secondary sources)
 - To understand the breadth of knowledge in the field of the subject
6. Researchers can infer the usefulness of a source of data's reliability and relevance by evaluating it with the following criteria except
- the reputation of the publisher

⁴ Ibid., 10.

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. 9th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 36.

- whether the source has been peer-reviewed
- the writer's nationality⁶**
- how frequently have others cited the source

7. Below are descriptions of different components of conducting a qualitative study, except

- Researchers use qualitative research studies to explore phenomena, explain behavior, describe an issue using nonnumerical data, understand phenomena, and collect participant stories
- The methodology of the study incorporates closed-ended research questions, the researcher's cultural beliefs, and biases⁷**
- The methodology answers several questions, namely, the what, the why, and the how of the study, to provide answers that describe the study problem, its purpose, the questions the researcher is looking to answer as well as the data he plans to collect to answer them
- The methodology of the study details the population, the sampling technique and adequacy of the participants, a description of the procedure for collecting the data, the system for data processing, and how quality assurance for the result's credibility, transferability, and dependability

⁶ Ibid., 45; 41–42.

⁷ Philip Adu, “Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study” (YouTube video, 2016), accessed September 8, 2022, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KRHvxY3N708>.

8. The following represent different methods of qualitative sampling except
- Homogenous sampling for focusing on participants who have similar experiences, beliefs, or background
 - Probability sampling to produce results that are representative of the whole population⁸**
 - Snowball sampling to recruit participants based on the recommendation of initial participant(s) sampled
 - Random purposive sampling to select participants who have been purposively sampled
9. One of the underlisted does not accurately describe the sections of the content of the entire dissertation
- The title page allows prospective readers an apparent way to locate the dissertation in a literature search
 - The abstract makes it possible for other researchers to determine the relevance of the particular work to their own studies
 - The methodology provides the basis for the study's conclusions and recommendations

⁸ Ibid., 42; 10.

- The conclusions and recommendations lay out other researcher's contributions to the body of knowledge, practice, and policy in the field of study**⁹

10. WHO's cohesive messaging and consistent writing style are applied to all its information products across media and present a mark of quality that strengthens its brand. Which of these is not compatible with the WHO style guide

- The guide recommends one of two referencing systems: Harvard and the numerical
- The WHO style guide only uses non-discriminatory language to ensure that its writing is unbiased and does not cause offense
- The WHO style guide avoids abbreviations with names altogether where the text is for an external audience to avoid confusion
- Capitalization should be applied to general terms and descriptive names such as "public health"**¹⁰

⁹ Linda D. Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*. Fourth Edition (Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019), 65–87.

¹⁰ World Health Organization (WHO), *WHO Style Guide* (WHO, 2013), 22.

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